

SOCIAL SCIENCES

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN E-WORKING ADOPTION AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE AMONG ACADEMIC STAFF IN UNIVERSITIES IN SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance among academic staff in Universities in southwest, Nigeria. The issue of work-life balance has become an issue of great concern to all practitioners and experts including employers of labour, employees, government agencies, policy makers, academicians etc. With the adoption of E-working among university academic staff, there's need to investigate how this new work order affect the work-life balance of employees knowing full well that their daily activities was centred around the four walls of classroom before the adoption of E-working after the COVID-19 pandemic. The study was a survey, in which Ex post facto and exploratory research design was adopted and a total of 694 participants took part in the study. Questionnaire format was employed for data collection, obtained data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics, utilizing the SPSS version 21.0 package.

The findings showed that there was a significant relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance among academic staff in Universities in South-West, Nigeria $\{r(692) = .22^{**}, p < .01\}$; there was no significant relationship between E-working adoption and leisure activities (a dimension of work-life balance) among academic staff in Universities in South-West, Nigeria $(r(692) = .07, p > .05)$; there was a significant and positive relationship between E-working adoption and personal life (a dimension of work-life balance) among academic staff in Universities in South-West, Nigeria $(r(692) = .28^{**}, p < .01)$. It was hence concluded that there's a significant relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance among academic staff in universities in southwest, Nigeria.

Keywords: E-working adoption, Work-life balance, Academic staff and Universities.

Introduction

Work-life balance issue is a recurring decimal among employees in the workplace. This issue has become an issue of great concern to all practitioners and experts including employers of labour, employees, government agencies, policy makers, academicians, researchers e.t.c. (Nwagbara, 2020; Awobona & Ojo, 2024). An employee is regarded as the most prestigious factor of production whose commitment is expected to be in tandem with the vision of an organization (Nwagbara, 2020). Studies have shown that the pressure faced by employees while managing their personal life with work activities is enormous to the extent that employees seek any available means to manage this anormally that is in relation with work-life balance (Akinbo & Ayodele, 2022). The implication of this anormally could result in serious consequences in terms of commitment on the productivity of an employee (Akinbo & Ayodele, 2022).

Work-life balance can be regarded as the division of an employee's time and focus between working and family activities (D'Andrea, 2022). Work-life balance is also the accomplishment of role related expectations that are negotiated and shared between an individual and his/ her role-related partners in the work and family domains (Brough et al., 2020). The academic field in Nigeria is also engulfed with the issue of work-life balance. Studies have indicated that academic staff due to heavy academic curriculum and shortage of staff in Nigerian Universities has become a serious burden on

the available work force (Ayotunde, 2016). They are expected to battle seriously with the problem of work-life balance to the extent that some academic staff are faced with the dilemma of switching career or traveling abroad in an attempt to solve the problem of work-life balance (Ayotunde, 2016).

All these were peculiar issues with work-life balance before the outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic. The outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic which hit the world in the first quarter of 2020 herald an unprecedented and unimaginable event in the world. The entire human race witnessed a global pandemic which affected local and international transaction and interactions and also, mode of operation (Tull et al., 2020; Whenham et al., 2020; Makibbin & Fernando, 2020). The novel corona virus disease COVID-19 pandemic hit the world and changed the everyday routine of individuals, employee and organisations globally (Eze et al., 2021). Industries, locally and internationally were not spared by the consequences of the pandemic wave. Series of studies were conducted on the menace of the COVID-19 pandemic in the global south as well obtainable in the Western countries (Berube & Bedeman, 2020; Baldwin & Weder-di-Mauro, 2020; Falaye, 2020; Aladejebi, 2021). The causes experiences and effects of COVID-19 pandemic have been investigated by numerous scholars universally (Falaye, 2020; Huaing et al., 2020; Nnadozie, 2020; Odekunle, 2020; Alon et al., 2020;

Baldwin & Weder-di-mauro, 2020; Mclean, 2020) and considered huge.

In Nigeria, the academic industries most especially the tertiary institutions were massively affected by the varying changes brought about the presence of the global pandemic. The phobia of COVID-19 pandemic eventually necessitated a force lockdown on the lecturers, students and entire university communities in the country irrespective of ownership (Enemu & Okigbo, 2021). However, the COVID-19 outbreak and the subsequent lockdown lead to a new work order (E-working) which forced many organisations to move to a virtual style of operation in place of the regular occurring physical interaction (Olanipekun et al., 2021). The academic circle were not left out. The technologies adopted by several academic institutions vary globally but, the common ones according to Manzoor and Hamid (2021) includes, zoom, microsoft teams, google classroom, whatsapp video etc. Similarly, claims have been made that E-working put academic employee's under greater stress than it alleviates, especially when new technologies and applications are adopted (Berube & Bateman, 2020). However, there have been no concrete empirical research on this, which is one of the focus of this study.

The required switch over to E-working is another major source of worry. These worries centered more on how academic staff handled using ICT for teaching and research, as well as how they handled the demands of their families while working from home (Beno, 2020). There were insinuations that some academic staff began to experience difficulty in operating and managing these newly imposed pedagogical platform for academic purposes alongside demands for attention from their family in South-west, Nigeria (Aladejebi, 2021).

The aim of this study is to determine if the adoption of E-working has eliminated the work-life balance concern that earlier studies were unable to fully capture when the majority of Nigeria universities operated behind four walls.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to examine how E-working adoption affects the work-life balance among academic staff in universities in south-west, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. determine the relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance among academic staff in Universities in South-west, Nigeria.
- ii. examine the relationship between E-working adoption and leisure activities (a dimension of work-life balance) among academic staff in Universities in South-west, Nigeria.
- iii. investigate the relationship between E-working adoption and personal life (a dimension of work-life balance) among academic staff in Universities in South-west, Nigeria.

Research hypotheses

The following hypotheses were generated for the study;

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance among academic staff in Universities in South-west, Nigeria.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between E-working adoption and leisure activities among academic staff in Universities in South-west, Nigeria.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between E-working adoption and personal life among academic staff in Universities in South-west, Nigeria.

Literature Review

The Concept of E-Working

Basically, E-working means the utilisation of ICT rather than commuting to work (Beño & Soňa, 2019). According to existing literature, the concept of E-working is synonymous with teleworking, virtual working, remote working, online working or working from home (ILO, 2020; McParland & Connolly, 2020; Nzekwe, 2020; Charalampous et al., 2019; Troup & Rose, 2012). According to Charalampous et al. (2019), E-working has been practicable in many western countries and on the increase in developing nations prior to the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic. This was corroborated by Vyas & Butakhieo (2021) that E-working implies the act or practice of working at home using a computer terminal electronically linked to one's place of employment. E-working also connotes work done via adoption of modern information and communication technology (Delanoije & Verbruggen, 2020).

Globally, E-working thrives most in developed nations for corporate organizations with increased risks associated with daily interpersonal relationships in areas such as sensitive bio laboratories, security sensitive organizations which includes military and paramilitary agencies, aviation industries, financial institutions, educational institutions which mostly award online certificates, religious organizations whose devotees are not physically around church, mosque or other premises and the likes (Beño, 2018). Meanwhile, Beño (2021) observed an increased demand for E-working in today's knowledge-based economy. This is because the conceptual explanation given to E-working as teleworking is currently outdated. As such, there are numerous definitions of E-working which is only peculiar to the organizations adopting its use (Steele, 2022). However, the experiences of developing countries, most especially Nigeria differs in the operation of E-working (Sakpere et al., 2020). This is because despite the provision of basic technologies, gadgets and applications to fully adopt E-working, several organizations in Nigeria places priority on the physical presence of employees at their duty post to mark seriousness with the job, commitment and dedication and to put the organization at a vantage point to subject employees to moral and behavioural checks which may not necessarily be part of the terms and conditions of employment (Aladejebi, 2021).

Nowadays, ministries, agencies, directorates, institutes, academics, politicians and scientists combine adjectives such as informative, electronic, digital, tele-, virtual, cyber, flexible, global, nomadic, networked or simply e- (which connotes electronic) (Beño & Soňa, 2019). The concept of E-working is replacing a range of different terms, such as "teleworking, telecommuting, networking, digital nomad, nomadic work, flexi space, flexitime," which seek to describe the ways in

which modern information and communications technologies have made it possible for information processing to be carried out remotely (Beño, 2021).

E-working uses information and communication technology to allow work to be carried out independently of location (Beño, 2018), and it includes the e-worker working from home or remote office (full- or part-time), teleworker part time at home and part-time in the office or mobile e-worker (on the move), outside the home or office using modern information and telecommunication technology (ICT). Literature further revealed that E-working is an activity where an employee works part- or full-time at home, partly from home or on the road and the rest of the time at the workplace, possibly in different nationalities (Wolor et al., 2020). This kind of work includes off-the job work, remote desktop log-on, sending and receiving e-mails, data and files and developing ideas and selling products and services remotely (Beño, 2021). An e-worker is any employee who carries out E-working as defined above in an organisation in the Internet cultural era. E-working can bring substantial benefits for the employer, by reducing overheads, increasing productivity and improving retention; and for the employee, by balancing work and other aspects of life, better access to employment, and for society, by bringing significant economic and social benefits as a result of reducing the carbon footprint (Beidel et al., 2014).

Concept of Work-Life Balance

The term 'work-life balance' does not necessarily imply an equal balance between one's work and personal life. It simply means the capacity to schedule the hours of the two aspects in such a way that one leads a healthy and peaceful life (Paulose & Sudarshan, 2014). Work-life balance can also be defined as having a satisfactory or comfortable level of 'fit' between the multiple roles in one's life, resulting in a sense of harmony in life.

Research shows that employees who work long hours have a lower degree of work-life balance, while managers specifically are more adversely affected. It must be noted that the level of work-life balance varies through the different stages of one's life, depending on personal responsibilities. A satisfactory balance also varies from one individual to the next. For most people, it results from the following factors:

- i. The number of hours that an individual is required to work, and
- ii. The level of control that the individual has about when and how the work is done (New Zealand Department of Labour, 2007) Factors affecting work-life balance.

Based on research, the following factors caused employees to experience conflict between their work and family roles:

- i. Number of hours worked per week,
- ii. Amount and frequency of overtime required,
- iii. Inflexible work schedule,
- iv. Unsupportive supervisors, and
- v. An inhospitable organisational culture.

Several studies have shown that the most significant predictors of work-life balance are working hours, with regard to working outside normal hours such as

evenings, weekends and unplanned overtime. Work-life balance is threatened if people are too tired after work to engage with their loved ones at home, or perform any necessary work at home. Research shows that long work hours, job demands, care responsibilities and work-related travel, are negatively related to work-life balance. Research also indicates that employed women spend more hours on household activities than employed men and more hours on work and household activities in total. It can be concluded that women still bear the primary responsibility for home and child-care tasks irrespective of their employment status (Levy, 2012).

In the recent ever dynamic work terrain, individual(s) are faced with unpacked volume of challenges in making sure that there is a balance between work and family life. Irrespective of the various definition of work-life balance, very few have found an acceptable definition and concept as it can be seen as the way of adjusting the working pattern of an employee in order to combine both work and other responsibilities together such as caring for children or elderly relative. Thus, the term work life balance has its classical meaning of being an overall level of equilibrium of an individual where an evaluation of attainment of family responsibility meets, without encroaching with work life (Levy, 2012).

Theoretical Review

The study is basically anchored on Work-Family Conflict theory.

Work-Family Conflict Theory

Work-family conflict occurs when demands of work life create problems in fulfilling the demands of family life. Work-family conflict has been defined in terms of inter-role conflict in which role pressures from work and family domains are mutually incompatible in some respect, i.e., participation in work role is made more difficult by virtue of participation in the family role. Originally, work-family conflict was considered as uni-dimensional but it is now conceptualised as bi-dimensional, i.e., work interfering with family and vice-versa (Ivancevich et al., 2011). Most research on work-family conflict showed that its greater prevalence was among employees, thus a greater focus was on the extent of work interference with family (Freeman, 2017).

Three types of work family conflict were identified and studied by Greenhaus & Powell (2006). These are time-based conflict, strain-based conflict and behaviour-based conflict. When the time demands on one role make it difficult to participate in another role, it is known as time-based conflict. For instance, to complete a presentation and be present at a family event on the same evening (Illies., 2009). Based on the work-family framework, the earlier studies done by Freeman (2017) revealed that the most cited hindrance between work and family domain is the competing requirement for time. Thus, Maertz & Boyar (2011) advocated two forms in which time-based conflict. First, due to time pressures involved in one role, it becomes physically impossible to satisfy the time demands of another role

and secondly, despite being physically present and attempting to meet the demands of one domain, a person is mentally preoccupied with another domain.

The second type of conflict which is known as strain-based conflict occurs when psychological symptoms (anxiety, fatigue and irritability) generated by work/family demands spill-over or intrude into the other role, making it difficult to fulfil the responsibilities of that role. For example, an employee might be less responsive to her family's needs while preparing herself for an official meeting. Moreover, studies have identified that a negative psychological strain will lead to extensive time involvement in one domain, thereby reducing the time available for role performance in another domain which in turn will create conflict. Both strain-based and time-based conflicts are believed to share a number of sources despite being conceptually distinct.

Behaviour-based conflict takes place when expected or appropriate behaviour in the family role (expressiveness, emotional sensitivity etc.) is considered to be dysfunctional or inappropriate in the workplace. For instance, an assertive working style of an employee which is considered as a sign of success at the workplace might create an atmosphere of tension when displayed at home (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). Like a strain-based conflict, a behaviour-based conflict demonstrates a negative spill-over from one domain to another where behaviour in one domain is influenced by the behaviour desired and developed in another domain where by inhibiting role performance in that latter domain simultaneously. For instance, in a family setting wherein a warm, nurturing and cooperative approach is desired, an assertive and confrontational behaviour may be considered inappropriate or out of place. In terms of job factors, the amount of working time is regarded as the most powerful and enduring predictor that influences work-family conflict. In other words, the highest incidence of work-family conflict results from long working hours. In addition, health, work and family outcomes are influenced by work-family conflict which is supported by studies. For instance, greater depression, physical health complaints and hypertension results from work-to-family conflict while greater consumption of alcohol results from family-to work conflict. Work-family conflict and work outcomes such as performance, absenteeism, turn-over intentions, burn-out and job commitment were examined by a meta-analysis done by Kossek & Ozeki (1999). The conflict of family interfering with work is negatively related to work attitudes and performances according to the findings. Moreover, regardless of direction, conflict between work and family was related to lower commitment to work and organisations, care-related absence and higher turnover intention. A family outcome such as lower marital quality and family satisfaction is related to work-family conflict.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted exploratory research design and Ex-post facto. Exploratory research design was considered because the relationship between the selected variables was adequately explored against other

studies. Also, ex-post facto design was considered because the focus of the study is on a past event.

Population of the Study

The population of the study was 3,179 as at the time of the study. The study was conducted in five universities in South-west, Nigeria namely; Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago Iwoye Ogun State, Babcock University Ilisian-Remo, Ogun State, Fountain University, Osogbo, Osun State University, Osogbo and University of Lagos, Lagos State.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The sampling technique adopted for the study was proportional sampling techniques in which 25% of the total numbers of academic staff from each University were used. Further, simple random technique was also adopted. This gives every academic staff the chance to be selected for the study. As such, the sample size was given as 796.

Instrument

Questionnaire format was used for data collection in the study. The questionnaire was made into four (4) sections namely; Section A, Section B, Section C and Section D. Three (02) scales were used for the study. These are: E-working Adoption Scale (E-WAS) and Work Life Balance Scale (WLBS). The questionnaire covers the objectives of the study and was open ended and close ended. **Section A: Socio-demographic information about the respondents;** The section collected the socio-demographic attributes of the respondents such as: age, sex, marital status, number of children, cadre, highest educational qualification, university ownership, residency and religion etc. **Section B: E-working Adoption Scale;** The E-working Adoption Scale was measured using remote work-benefits and disadvantage (RW-B&D) scale by (Ignusci, Signore, Cortese, Molinon, Pasca and Ciavolino, 2022). The scale consisted of 14 items. It is a 5-point Likert scale with responses ranging from Strongly Agree (5) to Strongly Disagree (1). For the purpose of this study, the scale was adapted to suit the objectives of this study. **Section C: Work-Life Balance Scale (WLBS);** Work Life Balance Scale (WLBS) was measured using a 15-item Work Life Balance Scale (WLBS) developed by Hayman (2005). The scale consists of 15 items. A five-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) Agree (A) Undecided (UN) Disagree (D) Strongly Disagree (SD).

Administration of the Research Instrument

Copies of the questionnaire were distributed to a total sample of 796 respondents selected for the study. The respondents were selected across the five (5) Universities selected for the study. Out of the distributed 796 copies, only 694 were successfully retrieved.

Statistical Data Analysis

Collected data in the study were subjected to descriptive and inferential statistics. The response to each question was presented in frequency distribution tables and percentages. For hypothesis testing, inferential statistics of correlation, regression analysis were adopted.

Results

The results of the study are stated in this section. This section is divided into two parts, namely, test of

hypotheses and discussion of findings. This is clearly shown below.

Test of Hypotheses

Three (3) hypotheses were stated and tested in the study. The hypotheses were tested with Pearson, r correlation, using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSSJ version 21.0). The results are stated below;

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance among academic staff in Universities in South-west, Nigeria. The hypothesis was tested by Pearson, r correlation as shown in table 1 below:

Table 1

A Summary Table of Pearson, r Correlation Showing the Relationship Between E-Working Adoption and Work-life Balance among Academic Staff in Universities in South west, Nigeria

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Df	R	P
E-WORKING ADOPTION	54.74	7.256	694	692	.221**	<.01
WORK-LIFE BALANCE	38.19	7.791	694			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2024

The result in table 1 above revealed that there was a significant and positive relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance among academic staff in Universities in South-West, Nigeria {r (692) = .22**, p<.01}. Therefore, the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is a significant relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance

among academic staff in Universities in South-west, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between E-working adoption and leisure activities (a dimension of work-life balance) among academic staff in Universities in South-West, Nigeria. The hypothesis was tested by Pearson, r Correlation. The result is shown in table 2 below:

Table 2

A Summary Table of Pearson, r Correlation Showing the Relationship Between E-Working Adoption and Leisure Activities (a Dimension of Work-life Balance) among Academic Staff in Universities in South West, Nigeria.

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Df	r	P
E-WORKING ADOPTION	54.74	7.256	694	692	.07	>.05
LEISURE ACTIVITIES	5.43	1.611	694			

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2024

The result in table 2 above revealed that there was no significant relationship between E-working adoption and leisure activities (a dimension of work-life balance) among academic staff in Universities in South-West, Nigeria (r (692) = .07, p>.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby accepted while the alternative hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is significant relationship between E-working adoption and leisure activities (a dimension of work-life balance)

among academic staff in Universities in South-West, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

There is no significant relationship between E-working adoption and personal life (a dimension of work-life balance) among academic staff in Universities in South-west, Nigeria. The hypothesis was tested by Pearson, r Correlation. The result is shown in table 3 below:

Table 3

A Summary Table of Pearson, r Correlation Showing the Relationship Between E-Working Adoption and Personal Life (a Dimension of Work-life Balance) among Academic Staff in Universities in South West, Nigeria

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Df	r	P
E-WORKING ADOPTION	54.74	7.256	694	692	.28**	<.01
PERSONAL LIFE	11.23	4.122	694			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author's Fieldwork, 2024

The result in table 3 above revealed that there was a significant and positive relationship between E-working adoption and personal life (a dimension of work-life balance) among academic staff in Universities in South-West, Nigeria (r (692) = .28**, p<.01). Therefore, the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is significant relationship between E-working adoption and personal life (a dimension of work-life

balance) among academic staff in Universities in South-west, Nigeria. This outcome is line with the study of Ganiyu, (2021) and Jacob & Fredrick (2022). The study found that logical explanation behind the finding is that, work-life balance is an issue of employee well-being related to the employee's capacity to manage personal life. Maintaining a good work-life balance helps to decrease stress and prevent burnout in the family life.

Discussion

This study explored the relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance among academic staff in Universities in Southwest, Nigeria.

The findings pertaining to (Objective 1), Hypothesis One affirms a significant association between E-working adoption and work-life balance among academic staff in Universities in South-West, Nigeria. This alignment echoes similar conclusions drawn by Bellmann & Hübler (2021) and Tejero & Ayoola (2022) in distinct studies conducted within corporate organizations in Nigeria. The plausible rationale behind this outcome lies in the essence of E-working, which transcends traditional office spaces and encompasses remote work facilitated by technology such as laptops, internet connectivity, and collaboration tools. Furthermore, James & Liadi's (2020) exploration of work-life balance among knowledge workers in the civil service of Nigeria corroborates these findings, revealing a positive correlation between E-working, flexible work arrangements, and work-life balance. The study underscores the pivotal roles played by organizational support, social support, and individual characteristics like self-efficacy in effectively managing work-life equilibrium.

The findings associated with (Objective 2), Hypothesis Two reveal a lack of significant relationship between E-working adoption and leisure activities, a dimension of work-life balance, among academic staff in Universities in South-West Nigeria. This conclusion finds support in the study conducted by Awobona & ojo (2024), who explored the impact of Socio demographic characteristics on work-life balance, specifically in the context of the banking industry. Finding, from (Objective 3), Hypothesis three contributes to the overall understanding by establishing a significant relationship between E-working adoption and the personal life dimension of work-life balance among academic staff in South-Western Nigerian Universities. This concordant outcome aligns seamlessly with the research conducted by Ganiyu (2021) and Jacob & Fredrick (2022), reinforcing the robustness of the identified association.

Conclusion

It is concluded based on the findings obtained in the study that;

There is a significant relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance among academic staff in Universities in Southwest Nigeria. A positive correlation was identified between E-working adoption and overall work-life balance, indicating that the integration of E-working practices positively impacts the equilibrium between professional responsibilities and personal life. E-working adoption did not exhibit a significant relationship with leisure activities among academic staff in the region. This suggests that while E-working adoption may enhance overall work-life balance, it may not distinctly influence the allocation of time to leisure activities. Furthermore, from the findings of the study, it was concluded that, there is significant relationship between E-working adoption and the personal life dimension of work-life balance among academic staff in Universities in south-west, Nigeria. This implies that the implementation of E-working has

a discernible impact on the personal lives of academic staff in Universities in Southwest Nigeria. In essence, the findings underscore the multifaceted nature of the relationship between E-working adoption and work-life balance, influenced by the unprecedented challenges posed by the Covid-19 pandemic. These insights provide valuable considerations for organizational policies and practices aimed at optimizing the well-being and productivity of academic staff in Universities in Southwest Nigeria.

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